

DIDACTICAL POSSIBILITIES OF USING SOFTWARE EDUCATIONAL TOOLS IN PREPARING STUDENTS FOR INNOVATIVE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *The use of software educational tools in preparing students for innovative professional activities. The purpose of creating animations, interactive tests, quizzes and using Active Presenter.*

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In connection with the development of computer technologies and their widespread use in human work, the demand for programs in a certain direction has increased. It is known that the design and development of programs is based on application goals.

Currently, Word, Excel, and Power Point programs have become everyday assistants for science teachers. Today's teachers have to, so to speak, learn new programs for each lesson, and not just use textbooks. As time moves forward today, teaching a child by activating attention during a 45-minute lesson is a complex process. Therefore, teaching children through various exhibitions and games allows them to develop their speech and expand their thinking horizons. Using the Active Presenter program will also increase the effectiveness of your classes. The program allows you to create animations, create interactive tests, quizzes.

Active Presenter is also an excellent e-learning tool with advanced video recording and editing capabilities, as well as the ability to broadcast to a wide audience, all happening on a computer. With Active Presenter, you can create a variety of eLearning content, including demo videos, software simulations, quizzes, and eLearning games. Supporting the ability to create a variety of scenarios through responsive design, HTML5 technology, and audience engagement features, Active Presenter is the best tool for creating any type of eLearning course. Using new programs, it is necessary to solve new methodological problems, deepen your scientific knowledge, and improve professional skills. During the lesson, the teacher can increase the clarity, interest and effectiveness of the educational material.

In the test settings you can answer and change the same test several times. Each test can be assigned a specific score. You can also give partially correct answers, mix questions and answers, set a time limit, show the result of each answer or show the result at the end of the test, and analyze errors.

Using these features, control tests can be turned into training tests. This is one of the quick and effective learning methods. You can attach various pictures, diagrams and formulas to the test questions and answers. Each form has certain didactic aspects. Control of the testing method is one of the important factors in testing the knowledge, skills and abilities of students. The level of completion of test tasks helps determine the mental level of students when studying educational material. Analysis of test tasks shows that: memorization, then expression, then transition to reproductive information, then to productive information, focusing on thinking improves students'

control of knowledge, helps them apply the acquired knowledge in practice. The higher the level of skill, the greater the number of mental operations.

A well-structured test task should encourage the student to think and answer using all the knowledge he has acquired. Test tasks should not be difficult for the student, but should provide an opportunity to demonstrate their knowledge.

Active Presenter allows you to enter nine different questions:

1. True/false 2. Choose an answer 3. Multiple answers 4. Essay 5. Fill in the field 6. Fill out several fields 7. Order 8. Press and drop 9. Scale

Drawing 1

1. Closed test in the form of "True/False" - in which 2 types of answers can be given to the question asked ("True/False", "Yes/No", etc.). This test tests the student's knowledge of the information.

Figure 2

2. A typical question slide in Active Presenter has four parts. The two main parts are the answer group and the slide title. The other two are in slide order. This test requires the student to differentiate between correct and incorrect answers.

Figure 3. Closed test with multiple correct answers. This test is a little more difficult than the previous one, and the student is required to know the correct answers and their number.

Figure 4. Essay test with text input. The answer is given by entering the answer into the line. This test is more difficult than previous ones, and the student is required to know the exact answer and enter it correctly.

Form 5. The student must fill in all fields. In this test, several problems are given in one question. However, when the reader finds simple answers, complex answers become self-evident. This situation teaches the student to think logically.

Figure 6. Alignment test. This test gives answers and requires you to put them in a certain order. This test is more interesting than the others because it also uses the navigation element. This test also requires logical thinking, but the answers are not self-evident, as in the compatibility test. Therefore, this test is more difficult and interesting than others.

Figure 7. Open test with number. This is a special form of open-ended test (type 4 test) that requires the student to know the exact answer and write a number on a line. However, the peculiarity of this test is that the answer to it can be given accurately, roughly or within certain limits. To do this, it is necessary that the test writer correctly formulate the question, and the student give the correct answer, understanding the second hidden meaning of the question.

Figure 8. Open test where text is entered into fields. This test correctly forms the student's written language (vocabulary, grammar, spelling).

Figure 9. Closed test in which text is entered into fields. This test is easier than the Type 8 test as it has answers and only requires students to think logically and select the correct one from the list by comparing the answers with each other.

It is desirable for a modern teacher to be closer to young people and learn how to create interactive tests created in the Active Presenter program to attract their attention.

- serves to increase students' interest in the lesson;
- provides many opportunities for a teacher's creative approach to his profession;
- Teacher education provides ample opportunities for distance professional development.

We must not forget about the norms of their use, emphasizing their importance in expanding the worldview of students. For this reason, a modern teacher must constantly work on himself, possess the necessary qualities for his professional skills as a person with broad creative thinking and able to effectively use advanced pedagogical and multimedia technologies.

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